

Kinetics of liquid-solid ion exchange reactions of calcium/hydrogen ions on cation exchange resin in non-aqueous media

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The exchange mechanism between $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{H}^+$ in mixed solvent (water-glycerol) media on KU₂-20 (cation-exchanger) using batch technique is described. The dependence of exchange speed on temperature, particle size of the sorbent material was studied in aqueous and aqueous-glycerol media. The results showed that the exchange process was controlled by the diffusion within the exchanger particles for the systems studied herein. The effective diffusion coefficients have been evaluated at three different temperatures. The energy barriers against the diffusion of exchanging ions have been estimated from the Arrhenius equation. Entropies of activation for the sorption processes have also been calculated.

The rate factor in ion-exchange process is of recognized importance for the economic and industrial employment of ion-exchangers. The ion exchange kinetics of simple metal cations, particularly of alkali and alkaline earth metal ions, on various minerals, inorganic exchangers, and organic resins in aqueous media have been studied by a number of workers¹⁻³. However, little attention has been paid to the kinetics and mechanism of the exchange process in non-aqueous media. Many organic solvents with varied properties such as protic/aprotic nature, dielectric constant, etc., have been used to study the behaviour of ion exchange selectivity in mixed solvent systems⁴.

The kinetics of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} uptake onto chelating resins (recovery from water) was modeled on the basis of the internal concentration profiles inside the exchanger bead. The study was complemented with measurements of bead size studies during the ion exchange process. The experimental results were discussed in terms of pseudo steady state kinetic models, and the effective diffusion coefficients were evaluated⁵.

The present work is an attempt to study the kinetics and mechanism of the exchange process of $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{H}^+$ ion with an aim to obtain information about the rate-determining step of the ion exchange process with varying polarity of the systems studied by way of different proportions (25, 50 and 75% v/v) of glycerol and water. The study was performed at different temperatures (18, 43 and 60°) and different particle sizes (0.2, 0.35 and 0.63 mm) of the cation exchanger. Experiments on batch contact for metal ion uptake and $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{H}^+$ interdiffusion

were carried out. The findings were expected to help in the understanding of the intraparticle motion of the ions.

Results and discussion

Rate expression and evaluation of kinetic and thermodynamic parameters :

The extent of exchange, F , at time t was determined as

$$F = \frac{\text{Amount of exchange sorption at time } t}{\text{Amount of exchange sorption at infinite time or at equilibrium}}$$

The equation, developed by Boyd *et al.*⁶ and later improved by Reichenberg⁷, has been applied for particle-diffusion-controlled rate processes. Accordingly, if the rate of exchange sorption is governed by particle-diffusion, the diffusion of exchanging ions through the exchanger is the slowest. The following equation is valid for diffusion through the exchanger particles :

$$F = 1 - \frac{6}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \exp(-n^2 Bt)/n^2$$

where n is the number of exchanger particles and B is the time of coordination. B is expressed as

$$B = \pi^2 Di/r^2$$

where Di stands for effective diffusion coefficient of the two ions undergoing exchange within the exchanger, and r for the radius of the particles.

Plots of Bt vs t must be straight lines passing through the origin. In the present study, for every observed value of F the corresponding Bt value has been obtained from Reichenberg's table⁷.

The energy of activation (Ea), associated with the sorption process has been determined by applying the Arrhenius type expression

$$D_i = D_o \exp(-Ea/RT)$$

The pre-exponential constant D_o gives the entropy of activation (ΔS^*) as

$$D_o = 2.72 d^2 \frac{kT}{h} \exp^{\Delta S^*/R}$$

where k , h and R are the Boltzmann, Planck and gas constants respectively, d is the average distance between the successive exchange sites and is taken as 5×10^{-8} cm and T is the temperature (K). All straight lines of plots of Bt vs t have been drawn following the method of the least squares analysis.

The rate of exchange can be determined by three different steps : (a) particle diffusion, (b) liquid film diffusion and (c) mass action. Consequently the rate-determining step of the ion exchange was ascertained by noting that the exchange rate was markedly dependent on the particle size of the exchanger. The results of variation of particle size of the exchanger are presented in terms of plots of Bt vs t . These plots show that the rate of exchange is inversely proportional to the particle size. This clearly indicated a diffusion-controlled process and not one controlled by the chemical interaction of the exchanging ions because in the latter case the exchange rate would be independent of particle size. Distinction between particle diffusion and film diffusion was then made by : (i) The nonlinear behavior of $\log(1-F)$ vs time plots (Fig. 1) indicates that the rate is governed neither by film diffu-

Fig. 1. McKay plots vs t as a function of temperatures : (i) 18°, (ii) 43°, (iii) 60°.

sion nor by a mass action mechanism². The shapes of these plots, called McKay plots⁸, are similar to those obtained for independent radioactive decay. The curves can be resolved into two linear components⁹ indicating the presence of two interdiffusion processes which comprise the overall rate of exchange, a faster one corresponding to the residual curve while a slower one corresponds to the later linear portion of the McKay plot. This observation is further confirmed by the shapes of F vs time plots, which indicates that rapid initial uptake is followed by slower uptake of the effective ions with increasing time. This suggests that the effective diffusion coefficients in the present system had two components which may be attributed to the simultaneous diffusion of the counter ions through the pores of different size and electric fields. It is also clear from the residual curves that with the rise in temperature the contribution of the faster component of the effective diffusion is increased. These observations are similar to those of Helfferich *et al.*^{10,11} who explained the variable interdiffusion coefficients on the basis of electropotential gradient along the diffusion path. (ii) The plot of the diffusion rate constant B against $1/r^2$ (Fig. 2) is linear, and the linearity of the dependence also confirms that diffusion within the particles is the step, which controls the exchange rate.

Fig. 2. Plots of B as a function of $1/r^2$.

The plot of Bt vs t at three different temperatures are straight lines passing through the origin, indicating that the rate-determining step is diffusion through the particle. The B values are calculated from these plots and are given in Table 1. It is seen from this table that the diffusion coefficient for the present systems of exchange sorption increases with increase in temperature, which indicates that such reactions are endothermic process. This is due to the fact that with increasing temperature the mobility of the ion increases and this to some extent overcomes the influence of retarding effect of addition of glycerol solutions. This is in conformity with the earlier observations of temperature effect on exchange diffusion coefficient⁶.

Table 1. Effective diffusion coefficients (D_i) and thermodynamic parameters for the exchange sorption of calcium ion at different temperatures

Glycerol % (v/v)	Radius of particle mm	$B \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$			$D_i \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$			$E_a \text{ J mol}^{-1}$	$D_0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\Delta S^* \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		18°	43°	60°	18°	43°	60°			
0.0	0.20	1.52	2.44	3.88	6.16	9.90	15.74	10.69	1.44	-86.00
	0.35	1.20	1.80	2.60	14.90	22.36	32.30	11.55	3.92	-77.68
	0.63	0.98	1.29	1.56	39.45	51.92	62.80	11.69	7.50	-72.28
25	0.20	1.13	1.60	2.56	4.64	6.49	10.39	11.55	1.24	-87.25
	0.35	1.05	1.20	1.95	13.05	14.91	24.33	12.36	2.76	-80.59
	0.63	0.81	1.06	1.40	32.6	42.67	56.36	12.99	6.79	-73.11
50	0.20	0.92	1.38	1.68	3.73	5.60	6.82	12.47	0.83	-90.58
	0.35	0.80	1.11	1.30	9.94	13.79	6.15	12.99	1.85	-83.92
	0.63	0.69	0.77	1.13	27.78	31.00	45.49	13.86	4.78	-76.03
75	0.20	0.83	1.23	1.52	3.37	4.99	6.16	14.41	0.75	-91.43
	0.35	0.70	0.96	1.21	8.70	11.93	15.03	14.85	1.67	-84.77
	0.63	0.52	0.75	1.08	20.19	30.19	43.48	15.40	4.55	-76.44

The data obtained (Table 1) indicate that the sorption of Ca^{2+} is greatly affected by the change of dielectric constant of the medium. It is clearly seen that the values of D_i are higher for exchange in pure aqueous medium (higher dielectric constant) as compared to these values obtained in presence of increasing proportions of glycerol (lower dielectric constant). The order of D_i values are $0.0 > 25 > 50 > 75$ % v/v glycerol-water media. Thus, the presence of glycerol has a retarding effect on the exchange rate that accounts for the lower value of D_i ¹².

It is found (Table 1) that the energy of activation of the exchanging cations in pure aqueous solution is usually low as compared with the values obtained in presence of increasing proportions of glycerol. This may be due to the low swelling of the resin particles in presence of organic solvent¹³.

The entropies of activation have been found to be negative for all the sorption systems studied. The negative values of ΔS^* has been taken as indicative of a comparatively higher degree of mobility and the lack of an orientational effect which the ingoing ions exert upon water environment¹⁴.

Conclusion : (a) Increasing the temperature leads to an increase in the extent of the exchange process and enables us to estimate its energy barriers. (b) Glycerol solutions (low dielectric constant) have a retarding effect on the calcium uptake and the rate of exchange process as compared to those in pure aqueous media (high dielectric constant). (c) The slowest step governing the rate of

exchange process has been found to be diffusion within the exchanger particles for all the systems studied herein.

Experimental

Calcium nitrate, nitric acid, glycerol, EDTA disodium salt, Murexide and sodium hydroxide were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used for preparing solutions.

The granular ion exchanger, namely $\text{KU}_2\text{-20}$ cation exchanger (H^+ -form), of exchange capacity 2.5 meq/g dry resin, moisture content (% by wt.) 30–35, was treated with $\sim 1.0 \text{ M}$ HCl for 24 h with occasional shaking and intermittent changing of the acid. The product was washed with demineralized water to remove any superficial acid and was finally dried at 40° , sieved (ASTM-E, 11-61) into three desired fractions (0.2, 0.35 and 0.63 mm) and then placed in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Kinetic measurements : Rates of exchange were determined by the limited batch technique^{2,15}. Calcium nitrate solutions (100 ml) in water- ($25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) HNO_3 with appropriate percentage of glycerol at constant concentration at $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ were shaken in a thermostat until the desired temperature was reached in stoppered conical flasks. Weighed amount of the exchanger (1 g) in H-form was added, and the flask was thoroughly shaken. After appropriate intervals, aliquots (1 ml each) were removed from the external solution phase and titrated with standard $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ EDTA solution using Murexide as indicator. The ion diffusion studies were conducted at 18, 43 and $60 \pm 1.0^\circ$ variation.

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